

Supplementary Analysis: YasudaK Model for Proton-Proton Collisions

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Abstract

This supplementary document provides additional details to strengthen the YasudaK Model for proton-proton collisions by incorporating laws of conservation, reaction channels, and quantitative insights. It aims to bridge the theoretical framework of the YasudaK Model with experimentally observed phenomena while retaining accessibility.

1 Introduction

The YasudaK Model proposes a geometrical mechanism driven by Gluon Balls and Meson Pi structures to explain phenomena in proton-proton collisions. Here, we extend the model by:

- Incorporating fundamental conservation laws at each stage.
- Introducing probabilistic estimates for reaction channels.
- Supporting theoretical insights with simplified quantitative arguments.

2 Fundamental Conservation Laws

2.1 Charge Conservation

$$\sum Q_{\text{initial}} = \sum Q_{\text{final}}. \quad (1)$$

For instance, the total charge of two protons (+2) must remain unchanged, even when particles like π^+ or e^+ are produced.

2.2 Baryon Number Conservation

$$B = +1 \text{ (for each proton or neutron)}. \quad (2)$$

Initial $B = +2$, conserved even when additional particles like mesons (with $B = 0$) appear.

2.3 Lepton Number Conservation

If leptons appear, their net number L must remain zero, e.g., e^+ ($L = -1$) must be accompanied by ν_e ($L = +1$).

2.4 Energy and Momentum Conservation

Total energy E and momentum $\vec{p}$ are conserved throughout:

$$E_{\text{initial}} = E_{\text{final}}, \quad \vec{p}_{\text{initial}} = \vec{p}_{\text{final}}. \quad (3)$$

3 Reaction Channels and Probabilities

3.1 Hadronic Channels

For moderate energies, typical reactions include:

These reactions have high cross-sections (σ) compared to weak channels.

3.2 Electroweak Channels

Electroweak channels require high energy and have smaller branching ratios.

4 Quantitative Formalism

4.1 Cross-Section Simplifications

A rough estimate of the cross-section for a reaction mediated by gluons:

$$\sigma \sim \alpha_s^2 \cdot \frac{1}{E^2}, \quad (4)$$

where α_s is the strong coupling constant, and E is the center-of-mass energy.

4.2 Decay Rates

For weak processes:

$$\Gamma \sim G_F^2 \cdot E^5 \cdot \frac{1}{\pi^3}, \quad (5)$$

where G_F is the Fermi coupling constant.

5 Gluon Ball Dynamics

5.1 Formation and Dissolution

Gluon Balls ($B = 0, Q = 0$) serve as transient states, decaying primarily into mesons:

$$\text{Gluon Ball} \rightarrow \pi^+ + \pi^- + \pi^0. \quad (6)$$

5.2 Experimental Implications

Although rare, these states could be identified through characteristic decay patterns and invariant mass distributions near 1 – 2 GeV.

6 Figures and Tables

6.1 Reaction Table

Reaction	Channel	Probability Estimate
$p + p \rightarrow p + p + \pi^0$	Hadronic	High ($\sim 10^{-2}$)
$p + p \rightarrow p + n + e^+ + \nu_e$	Electroweak	Low ($\sim 10^{-5}$)

Table 1: Sample reaction channels and their relative probabilities.

6.2 Diagram of Feynman Interaction

7 Conclusion

By integrating conservation laws, probabilistic reasoning, and quantitative formalism, this supplementary analysis enhances the scientific rigor of the YasudaK Model. Future experimental studies, such as those conducted at the LHC, may provide further validation.

Figure 1: Feynman diagram illustrating $p + p \rightarrow p + p + \pi^+ + \pi^-$.

References